

Formulation, & Evaluation of Polyherbal oil for Pain: A Traditional Ayurvedic Approach

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ABSTRACT: Herbal remedies have gained increasing attention as alternatives therapies for pain management due their minimal side effects and natural origin. This specific polyherbal oil is a traditional, plant- based therapeutic formulation designed for topical relief of Musculo skeletal pain, inflammation joint discomfort. By integrating common kitchen staples with medicinal herbs, the formulation leverages synergistic interactions to provide a safer, cost effective alternative to synthetic painkillers. This study focuses on formulation and evaluation of herbal pain relief oil using *trachyspermumammi*, commonly knows as carom seeds or ajwain. It also includes herbs like dried garlic, fenugreek seeds (ajwain), dry ginger (sunth), camphor, turmeric, *azadirachta indica* (neem leaves). Where mustard oil is used as a base. The oil was prepared using cold infusion technique. The formulation was tested for its efficacy in reducing muscle and joint pain. Results in reduce pain and inflammation.

Keywords: Garlic, Carom seeds, Dry ginger, Camphor, Turmeric , Neem leaves.

INTRODUCTION:

Polyherbal are all about combining the goodness of multiple herbs to create a potent remedy. Managing pain, whether short-term or long-lasting, is a universal health challenge. While conventional remedies like NSAIDs and opioids are common, they frequently carry risk of dependency and gastrointestinal issues, boosting demand for safer, natural alternatives. Herbal remedies, particularly traditional solution like carom seeds (ajwain), offer promising, potent, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic benefits, with thymol identified as a key active compound.

Pain management is a significant concern globally, and ayurvedic formulation offer a promising alternative to conventinal treatments. Polyherbal oils, infused with a blend of medicinal herbs, have been used for centuries in traditional Indian medicine to treat pain and inflammation. The synergistic effects of combining multiple herbs can enhance therapeutic benefits, making these formulation a

valuable area of study. This study focuses on a polyherbal oil formulation, using mustard oil as a base, enriched with ingredients like garlic, seeds, dry ginger, turmeric and others. We'll explore the cold-infused preparation technique, benefits, and potential applications of this formulation in pain relief, including its possible use in managing chronic pain, arthritis, and antioxidant properties of these herbs may contribute to the formulations efficacy, offering a natural and potentially safer alternative to conventional pain management options.

MUSTARD OIL BENEFITS:

1. "Mustard oil, with its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, serves as an ideal base for topical pain relief application".
2. "Traditionally used in ayurvedic massage, mustard oil enhances the absorption of bioactive compounds from the herbs".
3. "Mustard oil's omega-3 fatty acids and antioxidants contribute to its therapeutic potential in pain management".
4. "The anti-inflammatory effects of mustard oil complement the herbal ingredients, amplifying the formulation's efficacy".

Fig. Mustard Oil

***ADVANTAGES OF HERBAL PAIN RELIEF OIL:**

- 1.Fast-Acting Relief:** Rapidly absorbed into the skin to provide quick relief from pain.
- 2.Reduced Inflammation:** Contains anti-inflammatory herbs like turmeric that help reduce swelling and stiffness.
- 3.Natural Ingredients:** formulated with plant-based ingredients (like camphor and eucalyptus) with minimal or no artificial chemicals.
- 4.Improved Mobility:** Regular massage helps reduce stiffness, allowing for better movement and flexibility in joints.
- 5.Better Blood Circulation:** Massage with the oil stimulates blood flow to the affected area, speeding up recovery.
- 6.Minimal Side Effects:** Gentle on the skin and body, reducing the risk of side effects often caused by oral pain medications.
- 7.Relaxing Properties:** Offers aromatic and therapeutic benefits that reduce stress and help muscles relax.
- 8.Ideal for Chronic Pain:** Highly useful for long-term management of arthritis, backaches, and joint pain.
- 9.Safe for Daily Use:** Can be used consistently without developing dependencies or causing harm.
- 10.Easy to Use:** Simple to apply directly to the affected area at home, providing a convenient, non-invasive treatment option.

***ROLE OF SELECTED DRUG IN FORMULATION OF HERBAL ANALGESICS OIL:**

1.Garlic:

- Scientific name: *Allium sativum*
- Native place: Central Asia
- Common name: *Allium sativum* or Lissan
- Chemical constituent: Sulfur – containing compounds(allilin, allicin, ajoene, diallyl disulfide, diallyl trisulfide)
- Biological source: the biological source of garlic is the bulb of plant *Allium sativum* L.
- Family: Amaryllidaceae

Roles:

- The role of natural antibiotic (antimicrobial)
- The role of a cardio -protective agent
- The role of an immune modulator

- The role of prebiotic
- Enhances digestive system health

Fig:Garlic

2.Carom seeds:

- Scientific name: *Tachyspermum ammi*
- Family: Apiaceae
- Native place: India, Iran
- Common name: Ajwain or Carom seeds
- Chemical Constituents: Carvacrol, Thymol
- Biological source: carom seeds are derived from the dried ripe fruit of *trachyspermum ammi*.

Roles:

- Anti-inflammatory
- Analgesic
- Digestive Aid
- Anti Oxidative
- Soothes joint pain

Fig: Carom seeds

3.Fenugreek Seeds:

- Scientific name: *Trigonella foenum -graecum* L
- Family: Fabaceae(pea or Bean family)
- Sub family: Faboideae
- Native place: South Eastern, Europe, West Asia, and the mediterranean region
- Common name: Fenugreek or Methi
- Chemical constituents: Alkaloids, Steroidal Saponins, Amino Acids.
- Biological source: the biological source of fenugreek seeds is the dried ripe seeds of *Trigonella foenugracecum* L.

Roles:

- Hypoglycemic role (blood sugar control)
- Hypolipidemic role (cholesterol management)
- Galactagogue role (lactation support)
- Anti- inflammatory and antioxidant role
- Gastoprotective role (Digestive Health)

Fig: Fenugreek Seeds

4.Dry Ginger:

- Scientific name: *Zingiber officinale* Roscoe
- Family: Zingiberaceae
- Native place: Maritime Southeast Asia, India, South central China, and Eastern Himalaya
- Common name: dry ginger, dried ginger, ginger root (technically a rhizome), Sonth, Shunthi or Shunti, Aale (Marathi)
- Chemical constituents: Phenolic compounds (shagaols, gingerols, zingerone)
- Biological source: dry ginger is derived from the dried rhizomes of *zingiber officinale* roscoe.

Roles:

- Digestive stimulants
- Potent Anti- Inflammatory
- Respiratory cleanser (Expectorant)
- Metabolic and Thermogenic
- Natural Preservative and Flavoring agent

Fig: Dry ginger

5. Camphor:

- Scientific name: *Cinnamomum camphora*
- Family: Lauraceae (laurel family)
- Native place: East Asia (specifically China, Taiwan, Japan, Korea, and Vietnam)
- Common name: Camphor laurel, camphor tree, camphor tree, gum camphor, kapur
- Chemical constituents: Terpenes and Terpenoids
- Biological source: natural camphor is primarily obtain from the wood, bark , and leaves of the camphor tree (*Cinnamomum camphora*)

Roles:

- Topical Pain Reliever
- Respiratory Decongestant
- Natural Insect Repellant
- Antimicrobial and Antifungal agent
- Spiritual and Ritual Purifier

Fig: Camphor

6. Turmeric:

- Scientific name: *curcuma longa* Linn
- Family: Zingiberaceae
- Native Place: Tropical south Asia (specially India, Sri.Lanka, and the eastern Himalayas).
- Common name: Turmeric, Haldi, Manjal, Indian saffron.
- Main Chemical constituents: Curcuminoids
- Biological source: turmeric is derived from the dried rhizomes of *curcuma longa* Linn.

Roles:

- Powerful Anti- inflammatory Agent
- Potent Antioxidant
- Brain Health Supporter
- Heart Health Protector
- Natural Digestive

Fig:Turmeric

7. Neen Leaves:

- Scientific name: *Azadirachta indica*
- Family: Meliaceae
- Native place: India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, sri. Lanka, and Myanmar.
- Common name: Neem, nimtree, Indian lilac, margosa, nimba
- Chemical constituents: Limonoids, Phenolics, Sterols.
- Biological Source: the biological source of neem leaves is the tree *Azadirachta indica* A.

Roles:

- Antibacterial and Antiviral Agent
- Natural Pesticide and Insecticide
- Immune System Booster
- Oral Health Support
- Anti- Diabetic Management

Fig: Neem Leaf

➤ **For 100ml Oil preparation**

Sr. no.	Ingredients	Quantity
1.	Mustard oil	100ml
2.	Garlic	2-3 cloves of garlic
3.	Carom seeds	1 tsp
4.	Fenugreek seeds	1-2 tsp
5.	Dry ginger	1tsp1
6.	Camphor	1-2
7.	Turmeric	1 tsp
8.	Neem leaves	A handful of fresh neem leaves

Fig: List of Material

➤ **METHOD OF PREPARATION:**

Step 1. Dry roast seeds: Heat a pan on low flame and dry roast the carrom seeds and Panublic seeds for 2-3 minutes or until fragrant. Cool and crush them correctly

Step2. Prepare the herbs: crush the garlic cloves and chop the leaves

Step3. Mix the ingredients: In a clean, dry glass jar, add the crushed garlic, roasted seeds, dry ginger powder, turmeric powder, and chopped leaves.

Step 4. Add mustard oil: Pour the mustard oil into jar, ensuring the ingredients are fully Submerged.

Step 5. Infuse the mixture: Close the jar and keep it in a cool, dark place for 7-10 days, Shaking the jars every 2-3 days.

Step 6. Strain and filter: After 7-10 days, strain the oil through a clean cotton cloth or Cheesecloth into another clean jar.

Step 7. Temper the oil (optional): if desired, heat the strained oil and add a few more Crushed garlic cloves and dry ginger pieces for added flavor.

➤ **EVLUATION PARAMETERS OF POLYHERBAL OIL**

1.Physical Characteristics:

- **Color:** color is golden- yellow to brownish. Depends on herbs and oxidation ratio brownish tone might show aging. Golden hue is typically for mustard oil base. Affects product appeal.
- **Odor:** oil's odor is characteristic, pungent. Depends on herbs and essential oils Used. Indicates authenticity and quality. Pleasant or strong smell is normal. Aroma affects user experience. Reflects herbal composition.
- **Consistency:** consistency is the oil's texture/ thickness. Slightly viscous due to herbal extracts. Affects spreadability and application. Indicates presence of herbal components.
- **Viscosity:** 50-100 cp at 25degreecelcius
- **Spreadability:** evaluates how easily the oil spreads over the skin. spreadability is good.

2. Chemical Characteristics:

- **Acid value:** indicates the amount of free fatty acids present. A high acid value suggest the oil is becoming rancid. Acid value is typically $\leq 20-25$ Mg KOH/g is good.
- **Saponification value:** it helps to determine the average molecular weight of the fatty acid; it is crucial for ensuring oil's quality and identifying potential adulteration. SV around 180-190 Mg KOH/g is common. It depends on herbs and oil blends.
- **Iodine value:** Measures the degree of unsaturation in the oil. since mustard oil is high in unsaturated fats, this value helps monitor its stability and susceptibility to oxidation. iodine value for mustard oil is typically 90-110g. it indicates unsaturation level. It affects the oil stability and shelf life.
- **PH Value:** the ideal PH value for healthy human skin is slightly acidic, typically ranging between 4.7 and 5.75. this acidic environment is created by a thin film called the acid mantle. The PH value for herbal oil is typically 5.5-6.5 for skin friendly topical oils. Slightly acidic to neutral.

DISCUSSION:

A well -like substitute for synthetic painkillers are herbal analgesic oil, particularly whwn it comes to treating muscoskeletal pain, inflammation, and localized pains. Several components with anti-inflammatory, analgesic, muscle relaxing, and circulation boosting qualities work in concern to create the composition of herbal analgesic oil.

Combining traditional medicinal herbs like garlic, carom seeds, fenugreek seeds, dry ginger, camphor, turmeric, neem leaves with carrier oil like mustard oil which not only facilitate transdermal delivery but also have inherent therapeutic benefits.

CONCLUSION: Herbal pain relief oil provides effective and natural relief from daily discomfort and pain. With a selection of dried and true herbal formulas, it ensures soothing relief that doesn't trigger harsh side effects found in products that contain chemicals. Whether used to address aching muscles, arthritic joints, or inflammation, it facilitates your body's natural restoration process, so you can be more relaxed and mobile. The perfect choice to use daily, it's gentle yet potent therapy for any regimen.

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